

DISRUPTIVE INNOVATION CONCEPT IN SELECTED EU COUNTRIES

Michaela Krechovská¹, Kateřina Mičudová², Miroslav Špaček³, Emil Vacík⁴

¹ doc. Ing. Michaela Krechovská, Ph.D., University of West Bohemia, Faculty of Economics, mhorova@fek.zcu.cz, ORCID 0000-0002-1215-1418

² Ing. Kateřina Mičudová, Ph.D., University of West Bohemia, Faculty of Economics, pitrovak@fek.zcu.cz, ORCID 0000-0002-4432-0079

³ doc. Ing. Miroslav Špaček, Ph.D., University of West Bohemia, Faculty of Economics, mspacek54@gmail.com, ORCID 0000-0001-6042-3249

⁴ prof. Ing. Emil Vacík, Ph.D., University of West Bohemia, Faculty of Economics, vacik@fek.zcu.cz, ORCID 0000-0002-8729-4894

Abstract:

The aim of this paper is to explore the concept of disruptive innovation and the factors that influence the adoption of disruptive innovations in selected countries. Over the past decade, disruptive innovations have become a significant driver of innovation that supports a country's innovation performance. The ever-increasing impact of disruptive innovations and disruptive technologies on societal development has attracted the attention of both scholars and practitioners. This paper addresses some of the issues related to this new innovation paradigm. It also examines potential differences or similarities in the adoption of disruptive innovations across countries. The findings are based on qualitative content analysis and quantitative research based on a questionnaire survey conducted in selected countries. The paper indicates the growing interest in implementing disruptive innovations. Disruptive innovations are mostly created through collaboration with partners operating in the innovation ecosystem. In addition, networking is another significant driver of disruptive innovations that facilitates and accelerates the emergence of disruptive innovations. Based on the research results, it can be recommended to focus more on networking activities, as a relatively low increase in these activities was indicated in the studied sample. At the same time, the research did not demonstrate a significant increase in the innovation performance of companies measured by the ROI indicator. In addition, the results showed that there was no significant difference in the approach to disruptive innovations between highly innovative Western countries and former Eastern European countries.

Keywords:

Disruptive innovation, innovation adoption, collaboration, networking, innovation performance.

JEL Classification:

O31, O32, O33

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, when many companies face intense global competition, new technologies development as well as changing market conditions and changing consumer demand and behaviour, innovation plays an irreplaceable role. Firms and countries that are not able to innovate in such conditions quickly lose their competitiveness. Innovations become key strategic elements for achieving sustainable growth, have an impact on economic development and gaining competitive advantage (Damanpour & Wischnevsky, 2006). Zhu et al. (2023) emphasise the digital capabilities of enterprises, which can be a significant factor in transforming corporate resources into a competitive advantage, particularly when there is a high level of flexibility. In the context of firms' digital capabilities, most of the research is concentrated on several key areas,

including firms' innovation performance, service innovation capability, open innovation, business model innovation, and disruptive innovation (Olabode et al., 2023; Wu et al., 2022; Vilkas et al., 2022; Wan et al., 2023). In recent years, there has been a notable increase in the discussion of disruptive innovations and disruptive technologies.

Innovation is a key driver of economic growth and in this regard, researchers and policymakers are calling for a new approach to European innovation policy that would place greater emphasis on the development of disruptive innovations and the diffusion of new technologies across the market (Krieger et al., 2018).

Indicators of national innovation ecosystems and the innovation performance of European countries are assessed, for example, by the European Innovation Scoreboard (EIS), which was introduced in 2021 and provides a comparative analysis of innovation performance in EU countries, other European countries, and regional neighbours based on 32 indicators (European Commission, 2024a). Based on this latest assessment, which uses data for the period 2017-2024 for all EU Member States, the majority of EU countries have shown improvements in their innovation performance. Since 2017, the EU's innovation performance has increased by 10 percentage points (European Commission, 2024b). Based on innovation performance compared to the EU average, the EU divides countries into four different innovation groups (European Commission, 2024a):

1. *Innovation Leaders* whose performance is above 125% of the EU average (Denmark, Sweden, Finland and the Netherlands),
2. *Strong Innovators* with performance above the EU average - between 100% and 125% of the EU average (Belgium, Austria, Ireland, Luxembourg, Germany, Cyprus, Estonia and France),
3. *Moderate Innovators* with performance below the EU average - between 70% and 100% of the EU average (Slovenia, Spain, Czechia, Italy, Malta, Lithuania, Portugal, Greece and Hungary) and
4. *Emerging Innovators* with performance below 70% of EU average (Croatia, Poland, Slovakia, Latvia, Bulgaria and Romania).

For the further development of disruptive innovations and their investigation, it is equally important to address the factors that influence or can influence the adoption of this type of innovation and to be concerned with innovation performance at the level of individual firms, but also at the level of countries, and to seek to support their growth in innovation performance with appropriate instruments.

1. DISRUPTIVE INNOVATION CONCEPT

The theory of disruptive innovation was first introduced in 1995 and has since been considered an effective way of managing innovation-driven growth (Christensen et al., 2015). The theory focuses on new technologies or business models and their impact on disrupting industries and the emergence of new market leaders. When a new technology or a new business model is introduced to the market and gradually displaces established products, services or entire industries, we can talk about a disruptive innovation. Christensen's book "The Innovator's Dilemma" (1997) is then considered to be the key literature associated with the issue of disruptive innovations, where the author points out that even established companies can do everything right and still lose their market leadership. Since then, the disruptive innovation theory has become the subject of interest of researchers around the world and across various fields, who are trying to explore the validity of this theory in various contexts, but also in practical examples (Si et al., 2020; Si & Chen, 2020, Nagy et al., 2016).

Disruptive innovation brings new performance criteria based on the use of new technologies or new product configuration and thus has the potential to fundamentally change markets (Christensen, 1997; Christensen & Raynor, 2003). Disruptive innovation involves the introduction of new products with different performance characteristics that differ from those of existing products (Christensen et al., 2015; Zhang et al., 2023). Initially, these new products only appeal to developing segments of the market. However, they have the potential to further develop and may have an impact on original technologies and products (Govindarajan et al., 2011). So disruptive innovation is a key strategy for creating opportunities to gain and sustain competitive advantage

(Ganguly et al., 2022; Kraus et al., 2023). Disruptive innovations are typically characterised by considerable uncertainty, high risk and longevity. Therefore, they not only impact the current technological paradigm but also transform the competitive landscape in the market (Antonio & Kanbach, 2023).

The term 'disruptive innovation' is often used incorrectly to describe any change or new threat. There is also a lack of understanding of the theoretical concept of disruptive innovation (Christensen et al., 2015).

Christensen (1997) presents three basic elements related to disruption innovations:

(1) Technological advances are outpacing customer demand for better technology in many industries. As a result, firms operating in the market can deliver more advanced, better performing and functionally superior products than customers are currently demanding. This creates a gap in the market between customer needs and the products provided by firms, creating an opportunity for new market entrants.

(2) It is also important to distinguish between different types of innovation, whether they are technological or business model innovations. In many cases, these are sustaining innovations, which improve products along the dimensions that ordinary customers demand, allowing firms to sell their products to existing customers with higher profit margins. It is important to distinguish them from disruptive innovations, which offer a new combination of product features that appeal to marginal customers, especially at the lower end of the market (see also Markman & Waldron, 2014). Additionally, they may initially exhibit inferior performance characteristics, lower cost, smaller size, or enhanced convenience.

(3) The profitability of existing customers does not encourage incumbent firms to pursue disruptive innovations targeting smaller markets and lower profit margins. New firms with few or no customers may be more interested in innovations.

As stated by Zhang et al. (2023), new market entrants can attack the market, change its rules or even disrupt existing incumbent firms by introducing new technologies, products or new business models. Indeed, disruptive innovation is not about improving existing products and services, but about creating entirely new value that disrupts traditional markets (Antonio & Kanbach, 2023). New market entrants that enter the market later have limited commitment and much more flexibility for disruptive innovation (Radnejad & Vredenburg, 2019). This allows them to commercialise disruptive technologies and makes them ideal targets for disruptive innovation (Hart & Christensen, 2002). Ho (2021) not only broadened Christensen's concept of low-end disruption by addressing high-end disruption but also drew attention to adopter categories. Adopter groups have various characteristics and sizes that play a critical role in the diffusion process of disruptive innovation. Both low-end and high-end disruptive innovation drivers were given attention. Chen, Zhu & Zhang (2017) revealed that factors influencing high-end disruptive innovation include government support, external knowledge sources, strategic support, and dominant position of R&D; while the factors influencing low-end disruptive innovation are cooperation with venture capitalists, external knowledge sources, dominant position of R&D, and entrepreneurs' innovation willingness.

The focus of value creation has shifted from individual firm value creation to ecosystem value co-creation (Jacobides et al., 2018). Consequently, disruptive innovations and technologies are frequently the result of collaboration between multiple firms, rather than the work of a single entity. Innovation ecosystem comprises several different participants, including both core and complementary firms (Ansari et al., 2016; He et al., 2023). As Kreschmer et. al. (2022) stated, recent development has transformed inter-firm competition into inter-ecosystem competition.

Later entrant firms seeking disruptive innovation often find it necessary to collaborate with other partners in the ecosystem (Gadde, Huemer & Hakansson, 2003). However, entrepreneurial ecosystems can assist later entrant firms in addressing resource constraints (Buhalis, O'Connor & Leung, 2023). The potential of entrepreneurial ecosystems is optimised when firms transition from competition to collaboration with the objective of joint value creation (Buhalis, 2020). The characteristics of a particular ecosystem then facilitate or, conversely, act as a barrier to the emergence of disruptive innovations (Rieple & Kapetaniou, 2017). As Bharadwaj et al. (2013) recommend, it is preferable to examine the impact of disruptive innovations on the

ecosystem, rather than focusing on the impact on individual firms later coming to market. The existence of a functioning entrepreneurial ecosystem is a crucial factor in the promotion of disruptive innovation. By fostering collaboration within the ecosystem, later market entrants can connect with other qualified actors, leading to the co-development of disruptive technologies. This will facilitate the growth of other market participants. However, later entrant firms should focus not only on disruptive innovation but also on market disruption to ensure they can identify new value and achieve the long-term sustainability of their disruptive innovation. Motivating and attracting other participants will then help accelerate the development and commercialisation of innovative technologies (Zhiwei He & Xinbo Sun, 2023).

2. DISRUPTIVE INNOVATION ADOPTION

In general, innovation adoption process represents the mental process through which an individual pass from the first hearing about an innovation to a final adaptation. It should be distinguished from innovation diffusion process that refers to spreading new idea from the resource of invention or creation to its ultimate users or adopters. Innovation adoption process usually observes stepwise process consisting of three stages (Pichlak, 2016):

- Initiation (pre-adoption stage) - when a staff within the organization becomes aware of innovation and access information to be able to make a decision.
- Adoption decision (established adoption stage) – where the organization decides if to proceed and commit to innovation. Strategic, financial and technological decision is made.
- Implementation – where the company puts the innovation into practice and makes it work.

Brand & Huizing (2008) explored the factors that accelerated or moderated the adoption of innovation. They concluded that knowledge, potential value, implementation or satisfaction were revealed to be factors that affected innovation adoption process.

The principles of the adoption of disruptive innovation observe similar principles as those relating to innovation as such (Molina-Morales et al., 2018; Morizet et al., 2022).

Researchers and policy makers have stressed the importance of enabling the diffusion of disruptive innovations across firms, sectors and countries (European Commission, 2017). In order to achieve this, it is essential to encourage firms to undertake risky innovation projects with potentially high rewards. Furthermore, policies need to be implemented to ensure the adoption of new technologies across the European economy. The dissemination of such innovations could be further supported by the introduction of dedicated support programmes and the strengthening of the European market for financing innovative firms, with a particular focus on SMEs (Krieger et al., 2018). But there are also other factors that influence the adoption and development of disruptive innovation. Many authors and industry experts agree that a key factor in today's business landscape is the collaborative approach and partnerships that drive significant innovations. This new paradigm for innovation is centred on fostering collaboration between diverse stakeholders.

Innovation ecosystems consist of a network of partners, including businesses, start-ups, government agencies, knowledge institutions, investors and end-users, who collaborate to co-create and explore innovation ideas and scenarios. This collaborative approach offers a unique value proposition for all partners, enabling them to address challenges or pursue opportunities that would have been unattainable alone (Oudejans, 2024). Whether a single company, knowledge institution or government agency, all partners benefit from the ecosystem's synergy, fostering innovation and growth. Innovation partnerships can offer a number of benefits, such as: the offsetting of R&D costs, the addition of expertise and flexibility, and the creation of new markets. Furthermore, they have the potential to accelerate the timetable for innovation and commercialisation, a vital function given that breakthroughs can otherwise take decades to achieve and commercialise. It is therefore unsurprising that 94% of technology industry executives consider innovation partnerships to be an essential strategy (Cecchi-Dimeglio et al., 2022). According to Edwards (2016), the next phase of innovation will be driven by collaborative partnerships across various geographic, economic, and

sectoral areas. Organisations that excel in cross-company, cross-market, and global collaboration are more likely to gain a competitive edge in the market.

Inter-company relationships among the firms operating within the same ecosystems can also play significant role. Molina-Morales et. al. (2018) proved that clustered firms as opposed to non-clustered firms possessed specific attributes that can influence the capacity of disruptive innovation adoption. They highlighted exploitation dimension to be a meaningful factor influencing disruptive Innovation process.

The position or reaction of incumbents to disruptive innovation have been thoroughly studied across various business sectors. For example, the customers in accommodation service sector can benefit from the disruptive business model by Airbnb. It was proven that early majority users can capture higher value than late majority users (Zach et al., 2020). Similarly, silver market represented fertile ground for both low-end disruption innovation and market disruption.

Health care industry is a meaningful beneficiary of disruptive innovation. According to Lai et al. (2024) adoption process of medical disruptive innovations can be viewed as a cognitive evolutionary process that sequentially establishes conformity, differentiation and normalization. According to them medical disruptive innovation is essential for deepening the reform of health-care system.

Cryptocurrency as a new paradigm may become a disruptor to national currencies. Cryptocurrencies arouse interest in society because they reformulate the generation and transference of money. Mendoza-Tello et al. (2019) affirmed that perceived trust, perceived risk, and perceived ease of use are not strong predictors of the intention to use cryptocurrencies and that the strength of their effects on the intention to use is determined by the perceived usefulness of adopting the mentioned disruptive innovation.

Uzuegbunam & Geringer (2021) investigated the impact of two unexplored variables affecting the adoption of disruptive innovation. These variables were cultural looseness, which is a norm-based measure of informal institutions, and global connectedness. Cultural looseness is significantly related to adoption of agricultural biotech. Global connectedness dimensions of depth and breadth are not directly related to adoption, only interactively with cultural looseness. These findings highlight the role of informal institutions and global connectedness in shaping complex interactions between disruptive innovation and industrial evolution within and across nations.

Disruptive technologies pave the way even in originally lagging business sectors as the agricultural business. Curry et al. (2021) examined socio-economic factors facilitating or constraining adoption in underdeveloped countries. No surprise that the involvement of women into production process facilitated adoption of disruptive innovation in New Guinea.

3. METHODOLOGY

The aim of the research is to examine the factors that influence the adoption of disruptive innovations and innovation performance trends in selected countries. Based on literature review regarding adoption of disruptive innovation and while revealing current disproportions in the level of innovation in European Union countries (Ziolo & Luty, 2023) following research questions (RQs) were derived:

RQ1: What effect of collaborative approach to disruptive innovation development can be observed?

RQ2: What is the impact of innovation networking on the development of disruptive innovation?

RQ3: What trends in innovation performance of companies that use disruptive innovation can be indicated?

RQ4: What are the differences in innovation performance among EU states with different socio-economic characteristics?

Research questions were formulated in consonance with recommendation of Bryman & Bell (2015, p. 92).

Research design is based on triangular approach using combination of qualitative content analysis and quantitative research. The role of disruptive innovation and its adoption was mapped out through qualitative content analysis. Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus were the databases subjected to search in course of time 2010-2024. Searching code “disruptive innovation*” AND “adoption” was applied. The former was

searched in the title, the latter in topic. Having completed the first search run, 50 papers bearing relation to the topic of this paper were collected. After shortlisting and removal duplicities it was collected 41 papers, that were listed in this paper.

For data collection in quantitative research, a questionnaire survey was preferred. Data sample was preferably collected through European Academic Network for Open Innovation (OI net) project during 2016-2018. Minor portion of questionnaires were collected in consecutive years 2019-2020. The data were collected in EU countries by the participating research staff in parallel. The survey was focused on adoption of selected innovation activities: scanning for external ideas, collaborative innovation with external partners (i.e. suppliers, universities, competitors etc.), idea & start-up competitions, using external networks (e.g. associations, intermediaries, knowledge brokers). The questionnaire was developed by OI net academicians and validated by external experts. Return on investment (ROI) of innovation activities was considered as a performance factor.

The selection of countries to be subjected to the research aimed to include highly innovative countries in EU (as Germany, Denmark, Finland), former post-Soviet countries (as the Czech Republic, Poland, Hungary, Slovakia, Latvia) and the countries that represent "moderate European innovators" (as Croatia or Greece). This portfolio of countries thus included countries with various innovation characteristics and enabled to create a representative picture of EU innovation environment. There were approximately 50 enterprises, respondents, from each country representing the main industries in EU (e.g. Financials, Information Technologies, Industrials, Materials, Engineering, Education, Energy, Health Care, Telecommunication Services, R&D). In aggregate, 497 valid responses were collected (response rate 38 %).

Cluster analysis was selected as a method of choice for the determination of similarity or disparity in innovation performance among selected EU states. This method represents a multivariate technique that classifies objects on a set of user selected characteristics (cluster variables). The resulting clusters exhibit high internal (within-cluster) homogeneity and high external (between clusters) heterogeneity (Hair et al., 2019, p. 192). The use of cluster analysis in this research was aimed at the classification of a data set (countries) as per criteria relating to level of innovativeness. The advantage of this methods is the possibility of working with various combination of variables or the ability to automatically determine optimum number of clusters including determination of the most significant variables within the data set. The outcome of the cluster analysis presented in the form of dendrogram offered clusters of countries with similar innovation characteristics.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This paper aims to test how chosen activities affect creation of a platform for disruptive innovation's environment. The study draws attention to frequency of the use of four innovation activities as scanning for external ideas, collaborative innovation with external partners, idea & start-up competitions, using external networks. The use of above-mentioned activities was compared with the performance trend measured by Return of investment (ROI) of innovation activities.

The research provided the following results and responses to RQs can be formulated in a following way:

RQ1: What effect of collaborative approach to disruptive innovation development can be observed?

The results of empirical research showed that the companies in chosen countries actively benefit from collaborative approach. 75.5% of companies surveyed report an increase in collaborative activities in order to disruptive innovation development compared to the previous period. Surprisingly, companies from countries such as Latvia, Slovenia, Slovakia or Greece also increased these activities significantly (the share of companies declaring an increase in these activities compared to previous years ranged from 87 to 91%). Companies preferably collaborate with other companies like R&D specialised firms, research agencies or innovation centres set up by state or regional administration, customers or universities.

RQ2: What is the impact of innovation networking on the development of disruptive innovation?

The frequency of responses regarding networking indicates a relatively low increase compared to the other selected activities surveyed. Only 61% of the firms surveyed showed an increase in networking activities for innovation development. The Czech Republic, Croatia, and Slovakia show a share of firms that increased innovative networking activities of only 36-52%. It is unfortunate that they do not maximise the potential of this tool to support the introduction of disruptive innovations. As demonstrated by other studies, participating in innovation networks enables companies to distribute the complex and challenging innovation process across multiple stakeholders, including innovation intermediaries, regulators, start-ups, and innovation centres, see for example Jacobides et al. (2018). These networks enable firms to benefit from networking and increase the efficiency of innovation development. In the line with Christensen et al. (2015), disruption can be viewed as a process typically involving small firms (often start-ups) with limited resources that challenge mainstream firms (established companies) by placing the products of small firms in a peripheral or new market base. Innovation activities are directed towards the constitution of new business models and platforms. These new platforms facilitate the exchange of goods, services, creating value for all participants (Parker et al., 2016; Dong et al., 2018; Zeng et al., 2017). They can quickly cause disruption by removing time and space barriers (Van Alstyne et al., 2016).

RQ3: What trends in innovation performance of companies that use disruptive innovation can be indicated?

The questionnaire survey showed that there were differences between companies in each country in terms of innovation performance, measured by Return on Investment (ROI). In Denmark, Finland and Germany, companies have indicated that they no longer perceive a possibility for significant further improvement in their innovation performance. This observation suggests that these companies have attained a level of innovation performance that is closest to their potential. By contrast, the largest share of firms that have seen a significant increase in ROI in the period under review is found in Greece and Croatia. It is important to note that, in general, 48% of the enterprises surveyed did not experience any increase in ROI during the period under review, and 12% of enterprises even experienced a decrease in ROI. This may be also due to the lag character of this indicator.

RQ4: What are the differences in innovation performance among EU states with different socio-economic characteristics?

Dendrogram constructed on the Figure 1 shows the hierarchical relationship among countries with respect to the factors included in the analysis (scanning for external ideas, collaborative innovation with external partners, idea and start-up competitions, using external networks). Countries close to each other have a short linkage distance that means a significant similarity. Countries connected very high have little similarity and have a large distance between them. The complete linkage method was used.

The shortest distance is between Denmark and Hungary. These countries are the most similar with respect to the factors included in the analysis.

The dendrogram shows four main clusters. The first one contains Denmark, Hungary, Finland and Germany. Germany joined the cluster last, and the linkage distance is quite long. The second one contains Greece and Latvia. The third one contains Slovenia and Slovakia. The last one contains Czech Republic and Croatia but with long linkage distance and then the objects are connected to cluster 1.

The same clustering scheme can be obtained when using Ward's method.

Fig. 1: Cluster analysis – dendrogram

Source: own research, 2024

The distance matrix (see Figure 2) shows Euclidean distances between countries, the similarity rate between countries in relation to the variables used.

Fig. 2: Cluster analysis – distance matrix (Euclidean distances)

Case No.	Euclidean distances (Spreadsheet12)									
	Denmark	Finland	Germany	Greece	Hungary	Croatia	Latvia	Slovenia	Slovakia	Czech Republic
Denmark	0,00	0,38	0,48	0,64	0,24	0,66	0,59	0,39	0,32	0,44
Finland	0,38	0,00	0,51	0,68	0,36	0,57	0,72	0,52	0,59	0,65
Germany	0,48	0,51	0,00	1,02	0,29	0,62	0,97	0,85	0,74	0,51
Greece	0,64	0,68	1,02	0,00	0,75	0,94	0,33	0,36	0,60	1,00
Hungary	0,24	0,36	0,29	0,75	0,00	0,51	0,74	0,59	0,47	0,41
Croatia	0,66	0,57	0,62	0,94	0,51	0,00	1,09	0,86	0,69	0,57
Latvia	0,59	0,72	0,97	0,33	0,74	1,09	0,00	0,39	0,65	1,01
Slovenia	0,39	0,52	0,85	0,36	0,59	0,86	0,39	0,00	0,37	0,76
Slovakia	0,32	0,59	0,74	0,60	0,47	0,69	0,65	0,37	0,00	0,46
Czech Republic	0,44	0,65	0,51	1,00	0,41	0,57	1,01	0,76	0,46	0,00

Source: own research, 2024

Cluster analysis separated 4 clusters. It is obvious from the dendrogram and the distance matrix that the shortest distances are not among countries that are generally considered to be innovatively high performing (Germany, Finland and Denmark), or between the former Eastern Bloc countries, or the countries that represent “moderate European innovators” (Croatia and Greece). The analysis does not show that the three groups of countries form separate clusters. It cannot be concluded that the former Eastern Bloc countries have a different approach to innovation than Germany, Finland and Denmark.

5. RESEARCH LIMITATION

The research was constrained by limitations in the composition of the sample of respondents. The selection of countries was made with the intention of ensuring the representation of the EU; however, a more extensive sample may yield more detailed results. The choice of instruments (activities) investigated in more detail to support the adoption of disruptive innovation was also limited, as there are of course other possible activities. The survey concentrated on the selected most significant factors that promote innovation and establish a

platform for a disruptive innovation environment. It will be useful to focus further research on performance measures of disruptive innovation and compare the results obtained.

CONCLUSION

The paper aimed to explore the concept of disruptive innovation and selected activities that contribute to the adoption of disruptive innovations and the creation of a suitable innovation ecosystem. Related trends in innovation performance were also not left out. The paper was based on a content analysis that searched for current literature and a questionnaire survey that examined various innovation characteristics of companies operating in selected EU countries. Overall, the research showed the growing interest in implementing disruptive innovations due to their economic benefits. It was confirmed that a collaborative approach, where companies cooperate with R&D specialized companies, innovation centres or universities, is a suitable activity from which companies benefit when implementing disruptive innovations. Therefore, an increase in these activities can be observed in the sample of companies studied across European countries, especially in countries that are included in the groups referred to as moderate innovators or emerging innovators. However, it is recommended to focus more on networking activities, which can help companies increase the efficiency of innovation development, as a relatively low increase in activities was indicated in the sample studied. In connection with the development of disruptive innovations, it is also important to consider the innovation performance of companies. The research did not demonstrate a significant increase in the innovation performance of companies measured by the ROI indicator in the monitored period, but it did show differences between companies in individual countries. However, the cluster analysis did not demonstrate a uniform approach to innovation among companies operating in highly innovative countries or, conversely, in the countries of the former Eastern Bloc.

Acknowledgement

This paper was created within the project BEAGLE – BLUE OCEAN STRATEGY FOR VALUE CREATION, Grant Agreement: 101131728, Programme: Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON).

REFERENCES

- Ansari, S., Garud, R., & Kumaraswamy, A. (2016). The disruptor's dilemma: TiVo and the US television ecosystem. *Strategic Management Journal*, 37(9), 1829-1853. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smj.2442>
- Antonio, J. L., & Kanbach, D. K. (2023). Contextual Factors of Disruptive Innovation: A Systematic Review and Framework. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 188(C). <https://doi:10.1016/j.techfore.2022.122274>
- Bharadwaj, A., El Sawy, O. A., Pavlou, P. A. & Venkatraman, N. (2013). Digital Business Strategy: Toward a Next Generation of Insights. *MIS Quarterly*, 37(2), 471–82. <https://doi:10.25300/MISQ/2013/37:2.3>
- Brand, M.R. & Huizingh, E.K.R.E. (2008). Into the drivers of innovation adoption: What is the impact of the current level of adoption? *European Journal of Innovation Management*, 11(1), pp. 5-24. <https://doi.org/10.1108/14601060810845204>
- Bryman, A. & Bell, E. (2015). *Business Research Methods*. Fourth edition. Oxford University Press.
- Buhalis, D. (2020). Technology in Tourism-From Information Communication Technologies to Etourism and Smart Tourism towards Ambient Intelligence Tourism: A Perspective Article. *Tourism Review*, 75 (1), 267–72. <https://doi:10.1108/TR-06-2019-0258>

- Buhalis, D., O'Connor, P., & Leung, R. (2023). Smart Hospitality: From Smart Cities and Smart Tourism towards Agile Business Ecosystems in Networked Destinations. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 35 (1), 369–93. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCHM-04-2022-0497>
- Cecchi-Dimeglio, P., Masood, T., & Ouder Kirk, A. (2022). What Makes Innovation Partnerships Succeed. *Harvard Business Review*. <https://hbr.org/2022/07/what-makes-innovation-partnerships-succeed>
- Chen, J., Zhu, Z.H. & Zhang Y. (2017). A study of factors influencing disruptive innovation in Chinese SMEs. *Asian Journal of Technology Innovation*, 25(1), 140-157. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19761597.2017.1302552>
- Christensen, C. M. (1997). *The Innovator's Dilemma: When New Technologies Cause Great Firms to Fail*. Boston, MA: Harvard Business School Press.
- Christensen, C. M. & Raynor, M. E. (2003). *The innovator's solution: Creating and sustaining successful growth*. Boston, Mass: Harvard Business School Press.
- Christensen, C. M., Raynor, M. & McDonald, R. (2015). What is disruptive innovation? *Harvard Business Review*, 93(12), 44–53.
- Curry, G. N., Nake, S., Koczberski, G., Oswald, M., Rafflegeau, S., Lummani, J., Peter, E. & Nailina, R. (2021). Disruptive innovation in agriculture: Socio-cultural factors in technology adoption in the developing world. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 88, 422-431. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2021.07.022>
- Damanpour, F., & Wischnevsky, J. D. (2006). Research on innovation in organizations: Distinguishing innovation-generating from innovation-adopting organizations. *Journal of Engineering and Technology Management*, 23(4), 269-291. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jengtecman.2006.08.002>
- Dong, M. C. Y., Zeng, F. E., & Su, C. T. (2018). Network embeddedness as a dependence-balancing mechanism in developing markets: differential effects for channel partners with asymmetric dependencies. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 47(6), 1-21. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11747-018-0614-5>
- Edwards, R. (2016). Collaborative partnerships drive disruptive innovation. <https://www.tcs.com/content/dam/global-tcs/en/pdfs/who-we-are/news/analyst-reports/Ovum-TCS-collaborative-partnerships-drive-disruptive-innovation.pdf>
- European Commission (2017). *The economic rationale for public R&I funding and its impact*. Brussels: European Commission.
- European Commission. (2024a). *European Innovation Scoreboard*. https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/statistics/performance-indicators/european-innovation-scoreboard_en
- European Commission. (2024b). *European Innovation Scoreboard. Executive Summary*. <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/ee134784-3e63-11ef-ab8f-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>
- Gadde, L. E., Huemer, L. & Hakansson, H. (2003). Strategizing in Industrial Networks. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 32 (5), 357–64. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0019-8501\(03\)00009-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0019-8501(03)00009-9)
- Ganguly, A., Talukdar, A. & Kumar, C. (2022). Absorptive capacity and disruptive innovation: the mediating role of organizational agility. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, 99, 1-12.

- Govindarajan, V., Kopalle, P.K. & Danneels, E. (2011). The effects of mainstream and emerging customer orientations on radical and disruptive innovations. *Journal of Product Innovation Management*, 28(1), 121-132. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-5885.2011.00865.x>
- Hair, J. F., Black W.C., Babin, B. J. & Andersson R. E. (2019). *Multivariate Data Analysis*, Cengage.
- Hart, S. L., & Christensen, C. M. (2002). The Great Leap: Driving Innovation from the Base of the Pyramid. *MIT Sloan Management Review*, 44 (1), 51–56.
- He, Y., Lin, T., & Zhang, S. (2023). Does complementary technology within an ecosystem affect disruptive innovation? Evidence from Chinese electric vehicle listed firms. *Technology in Society*, 74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2023.102330>
- Ho, J.C. (2021). Disruptive innovation from the perspective of innovation diffusion theory. *Technology Analysis & Strategic Management*, 34(4), 363-376. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09537325.2021.1901873>
- Jacobides, M. G., Cennamo, C., & Gawer, A. (2018). Towards a theory of ecosystems. *Strategic Management Journal*, 39(8), 2255–2276. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smj.2904>
- Kraus, S., Vonmetz, K., Orlandi, L.B., Zardini, A. & Rossignoli, C. (2023). Digital entrepreneurship: the role of entrepreneurial orientation and digitalization for disruptive innovation. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 193. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2023.122638>
- Kretschmer, T., Leiponen, A., Schilling, M., & Vasudeva, G. (2022). Platform ecosystems as meta-organizations: Implications for platform strategies. *Strategic Management Journal*, 43(3), 405–424.
- Krieger, B., Licht, G., & Pellens, M. (2018). New perspectives in European innovation policy, *ZEW policy brief*, 7. <https://hdl.handle.net/10419/183222>
- Lai, X.P., Zhang, W. & Chen, S. (2024). How can a single spark kindle a Prairie fire? Diffusion process and mechanism of medical disruptive innovation. *Chinese Management Studies*, Early Access. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CMS-10-2023-0555>
- Markman, G. D. & Waldron, T. L. (2014). Small entrants and large incumbents: A framework of micro entry. *Academy of Management Perspectives*, 28, 179–97. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amp.2011.0112>
- Mendoza-Tello, J.C., Mora, H., Pujol-Lopez, F.A. & Lytras, M.D. (2019). Disruptive innovation of cryptocurrencies in consumer acceptance and trust. *Information Systems and E-Business Management*, 17(2-4), 195-222. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10257-019-00415-w>
- Nagy, D., Schuessler, J., & Dubinsky, A. (2016). Defining and identifying disruptive innovations. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 57, 119-126. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indmarman.2015.11.017>
- Molina-Morales, F. X., Martínez-Cháfer, L., & Valiente-Bordanova, D. (2018). Disruptive technology adoption, particularities of clustered firms. *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development*, 31(1–2), 62–81. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08985626.2018.1537147>
- Morizet, D., Doyen, A., Dairou, V., Lebarbanchon, & Spinelli, S. (2022). Assessing user adoption of a new-market disruptive innovation: The LUD (Learning-Use-Deprivation) framework. *Food Quality and Preference*, 96. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2021.104385>
- Olabode, O.E., Hultman, M., Leonidou, C.N. & Boso, N. (2023). Disruptive market shift: conceptualization, antecedents, and response mechanisms. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 192. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2023.122577>

- Oudejans, D. (2024). Innovation through collaboration. *Compact*, 1. <https://www.compact.nl/articles/innovation-through-collaboration/>
- Parker, G., Van Alstyne, M. & Choudary, S. (2016). *Platform Revolution: How networked markets are transforming the economy and how to make them work for you*. New York | London. W. W. Norton & Company.
- Pichlak, M. (2016). The innovation adoption process: A multidimensional approach. *Journal of Management & Organization*, 22(4), 476-494. <https://doi.org/10.1017/jmo.2015.52>
- Radnejad, A. B., & Vredenburg, H. (2019). Disruptive Technological Process Innovation in a Process-Oriented Industry: A Case Study. *Journal of Engineering and Technology Management*, 53, 63–79. <https://doi:10.1016/j.jengtecman.2019.08.001>
- Rieple, A., & Kapetaniou, C. (2017). The Role of Business Ecosystems in the Building of Disruptive Innovations. In: *Academy of Management Proceedings*. Vol. 2017. <https://doi.org/10.5465/AMBPP.2017.15200abstract>
- Si, S. & Chen, H. (2020). A literature review of disruptive innovation: What it is, how it works and where it goes. *Journal of Engineering and Technology Management*, 56. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jengtecman.2020.101568>
- Si, S., Zahra, S., A., Wu, X. & Don Jyh-Fu Jeng, D. J. (2020). Disruptive innovation and entrepreneurship in emerging economics. *Journal of Engineering and Technology Management*, 58, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jengtecman.2020.101601>
- Uzuegbunam, I. & Geringer, J.M. (2021). Culture, connectedness, and international adoption of disruptive Innovation. *Journal of International Management*, 27(1). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intman.2020.100807>
- Van Alstyne, W., Parker, G. & Choudary, S. (2016). Pipelines, platforms, and the new rules of strategy. *Harvard Business Review*, 94, 54-61.
- Wan, Q., Tang, S. & Jiang, Z. (2023). Does the development of digital technology contribute to the innovation performance of China's high-tech industry? *Technovation*, 124, 102738. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.technovation.2023.102738>
- Wu, L., Sun, L., Chang, Q., Zhang, D., & Qi, P. (2022). How do digitalization capabilities enable open innovation in manufacturing enterprises? A multiple case study based on resource integration perspective. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 184. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2022.122019>
- Zach, F.J., Nicolau, J.L. & Sharma, A. (2020). Disruptive innovation, innovation adoption and incumbent market value: The case of Airbnb. *Annals of Tourism Research*, 80. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.annals.2019.102818>
- Zeng, F. E., Chi, Y. J., Dong, M. C. Y., & Huang, J. (2017). The dyadic structure of exchange partners' governing-agency social capital and opportunism in buyer–supplier relationships. *Journal of Business Research*, 78, 294-302.
- Zhang, F., Zhu, L., Xu, Z. & Wu, Y. (2023). Moving from reverse engineering to disruptive innovation in emerging markets: the importance of knowledge creation, *Technovation*, 125, 102791. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.technovation.2023.102791>
- Zhiwei, H. & Sun, X. (2023.) How do latecomer firms achieve disruptive innovation? A business ecosystem perspective. *International Studies of Management & Organization*, 53(3), 191-216. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00208825.2023.2246711>

Ziolo, M. & Luty, L. (2023). Disproportions in the level of innovation in European Union countries. *Scientific papers of Silesian University of Technology - Organization and Management Series*, 166. <http://dx.doi.org/10.29119/1641-3466.2022.166.57>

FACULTY OF ECONOMICS
UNIVERSITY
OF WEST BOHEMIA

Conference Proceedings – Business Trends 2024
Faculty of Economics University of West Bohemia in Pilsen

www.tvp.zcu.cz

ISBN 978-80-261-1270-9